

How to avoid statistical mistakes

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Reporting statistics

Methods	Results
Study design	Descriptive statistics
Diagnostic performance	Missing data
Multiple comparisons	Correlated data
Assumptions	p-values

Study Design

- Precisely detail eligibility and/or exclusion & inclusion criteria.
- Describe all tests and statistical procedures used in sufficient detail for an educated reader to redo the analysis.
- Include the sample size and/or power calculations.

Diagnostic performance

- Fully describe the reference standard.
- Detail the selection of tuning parameters, and how censoring was accounted for.
- Distinguish between internal or external validation (was there a split into training and test sets or cross-validation?).
- Describe the selection for cut-off values

Multiple comparisons

- State whether the intention was to generate new hypothesis or confirm a pre-specified hypothesis.
- Detail the method used for multiplicity adjustments or that none was used.
- Describe whether the analysis was pre-planned or post-hoc.

Assumptions

- The key assumptions for the analysis (e.g., normality of the distribution) should be listed and a description of their validity included.
- Include a description of methods used for confounding adjustment (e.g., regression-based covariate or propensity score adjustments).
- Survey response rate(s) should be reported.

Descriptive statistics

- Proportions should be accompanied by numerator and denominator values (e.g., for sensitivity and specificity).
- The number of significant digits should be justified by the sample size and the variability in the parameter reported.
- Include a table with the characteristics of the study sample, which is stratified in accordance with the main objective.

Missing data

- Report number of participants/observations with missing data.
- Use appropriate methods to account for missing data (e.g., multiple imputation, or inverse probability weighting).
- This also applies to analyses involving loss to follow-up (e.g., conduct intention-to-treat analyses).

Correlated data

- To account for multiple measurements, use generalised estimating equations or mixed effect models.
- In cases of paired or matched data (e.g., pre- and post-intervention measurements from the same individuals), use paired t-tests (continuous variables), or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (continuous or ordinal variables).

p-values

- Provide exact p-values, unless the p-value is <0.001 (then statements like $p<0.001$ are appropriate).
- Two significant digits are usually appropriate unless the p-value is <0.01 , in which case one significant digit is usually sufficient.
- Accompany p-values with point estimates and confidence intervals.

BIG NO-NO!

Presenting statistically non-significant findings as evidence of absence of an effect.

If the original study hypothesis is that no meaningful difference is expected,

then the study should be designed specifically to test non-inferiority or equivalence

(with appropriate tests and pre-specified margins).

How to report data

Categorical variables

Numbers and percentages

Continuous variables

Mean and standard deviation

Skewed data

Median and interquartile ranges

▶ **Units should always be reported.**

**Would you like to know what a
data analysis plan looks like?**

DM me for actionable feedback.

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